

A Physics-Informed Machine Learning Framework Coupling the SMAP Rainfall-Runoff Model with BiLSTM and XGBoost: Open-Source Implementation and Application to a Data-Scarce Semi-Arid Basin (Utinga River, Bahia, Brazil)

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Abstract

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Reliable monthly streamflow forecasting is essential for water resources management in semi-arid basins, where intermittent flow regimes and data scarcity severely limit the performance of purely data-driven approaches. This study proposes and evaluates a novel **Hybrid SMAP-LSTM** framework that couples the monthly rainfall-runoff model SMAP [Lopes et al. \(1982\)](#) with a Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) neural network [Hochreiter and Schmidhuber \(1997\)](#), augmented by a SMAP + XGBoost alternative. The SMAP model is calibrated via Differential Evolution to extract nine physics-informed internal state variables — soil moisture, direct runoff, baseflow, groundwater recharge, actual evapotranspiration, soil water deficit, and simulated streamflow — which are provided as additional features to the neural network. The framework was applied to the Utinga River Basin (Paraguaçu hydrographic region, Bahia, Northeast Brazil; $\approx 1,200 \text{ km}^2$; Köppen BSh) using 340 monthly records (December 1992 – March 2021). A rigorous ablation study compared five configurations: SMAP standalone (M1), BiLSTM with meteorological features (M2), SMAP-guided BiLSTM (M3), full SMAP-BiLSTM Hybrid (M4), and SMAP + XGBoost (M5). The SMAP + XGBoost model (M5) achieved the best test-period performance (NSE = 0.205; PBIAS = 3.97%; RMSE = $1.226 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$; KGE = 0.241), outperforming both the standalone SMAP (NSE = 0.132) and all BiLSTM variants (NSE ≤ -0.21). SMAP physics features improved BiLSTM test NSE by ≈ 20 percentage points over the meteorological-only baseline. The calibrated SMAP model yields $Q_{90} = 0.975 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$; the observed Q_{90} is $0.423 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, implying a statutory water concession limit of $0.338 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ under Bahia State legislation (CERH/BA Resolution No. 63/2020). The proposed framework is reusable for other lumped physical models and sequence learning architectures, and provides a practical template for physics-informed machine learning in data-scarce semi-arid regions of Northeast Brazil.

Keywords: Rainfall-runoff modelling. SMAP model. Long Short-Term Memory. XGBoost. Physics-informed machine learning. Semi-arid hydrology. Water resources management. Utinga River Basin. Streamflow forecasting. Q_{90} .

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1 Introduction

Monthly streamflow forecasting supports reservoir operation, irrigation scheduling, drought early warning, and water allocation in semi-arid basins [Collischonn and Dornelles \(2013\)](#). In Northeast Brazil (NEB), one of the world’s most densely populated dryland regions, water scarcity is chronic and episodic droughts cause severe socioeconomic impacts [Marengo et al. \(2017\)](#); [Cirilo et al. \(2007\)](#). The Utinga River Basin, a sub-basin of the Paraguaçu hydrographic region in Bahia State, experienced a prolonged drought from 2011 to 2017, triggering widespread water conflicts and motivating the Bahia State Secretariat of Hydraulic Infrastructure and Sanitation (SIHS/BA) to conduct feasibility studies for eleven hydraulic structures along the river’s main channel [SIHS/BA \(2020\)](#).

Two broad modelling paradigms have historically addressed the rainfall-runoff problem. *Process-based* lumped models — such as SMAP [Lopes et al. \(1982\)](#), HBV [Bergström \(1976\)](#), and GR4J [Perrin et al. \(2003\)](#) — encode physical process knowledge through governing equations, offering interpretability and robustness under data-scarce conditions. *Data-driven* approaches, particularly Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks [Hochreiter and Schmidhuber \(1997\)](#), have demonstrated remarkable skill in large-sample hydrology [Kratzert et al. \(2018, 2019\)](#). However, [Nearing et al. \(2021\)](#) showed that the relative advantage of deep learning over process-based models depends critically on the volume of training data, a condition frequently unmet in developing-country semi-arid basins.

The integration of physical knowledge into machine learning — termed *physics-informed machine learning* (PIML) [Shen \(2018\)](#) — has emerged as a strategy to bridge these paradigms. [Yang et al. \(2025\)](#) combined the Pangu-Weather atmospheric AI model with LSTM and GRU networks on the Beipanjiang River Basin (China), achieving NSE improvements of 8–12% over standalone data-driven models. [Kim et al. \(2024\)](#) applied LSTM to four stations of the Nam Ngum River (Lao PDR) and proposed using autocorrelation analysis to determine the optimal LSTM lookback window (sequence length), obtaining NSE values of 0.50–0.70. [Ghimire et al. \(2023\)](#) introduced DeepGR4J, hybridising the GR4J model with CNN and LSTM, achieving superior NSE in arid Australian catchments. [Xie et al. \(2023\)](#) coupled HEC-HMS with LSTM (Ia-LSTM) for event-based runoff modelling, outperforming both standalone models.

Despite this growing body of literature, to the best of the authors’ knowledge, no previous study has applied the SMAP model as the physical backbone of a PIML hybrid framework, nor has any PIML approach been evaluated in the Utinga River Basin or comparable NEB semi-arid basins.

This paper addresses the following research questions:

- (RQ1)** Can SMAP internal state variables serve as physics-informed features for a BiLSTM streamflow model, and what is their marginal contribution (ablation study)?
- (RQ2)** Does the SMAP + XGBoost hybrid offer a data-efficient alternative?

(RQ3) What are the Q_{90} reference flows and the implied water concession limits for Bahia State water allocation?

The main original contributions are: (i) first hybrid SMAP-LSTM framework in the literature; (ii) systematic ablation study across five model configurations; (iii) introduction of SMAP + XGBoost as a computationally efficient alternative; (iv) hydrologically informed Q_{90} and water concession analysis under CERH/BA Resolution No. 63/2020; and (v) a reusable Python framework available as supplementary material.

2 Study Area and Hydrological Context

2.1 The Paraguaçu River Basin

The Paraguaçu River basin is located in the centre-west of Bahia State, Brazil, covering approximately 54,877 km² and encompassing at least 40 municipalities [Gonçalves \(2014\)](#). The basin belongs to Atlantic East Hydrographic Region 5 (ANA coding 51), and to Bahia State Hydrographic Planning Region X (Paraguaçu). Approximately 67% of the basin has a semi-arid climate (Köppen BSh), with mean annual rainfall between 400 and 900 mm.

2.2 The Utinga River Basin

The Utinga River Basin is a right-bank tributary sub-basin of the Rio Bonito within the Paraguaçu system, located at approximately 12–13°S, 40–41°W, draining an area of approximately 1,200 km² (Figure 7). The climate is Köppen BSh with mean annual rainfall 550–750 mm concentrated in the November–March wet season. Mean annual potential evapotranspiration (Penman-Monteith FAO) exceeds 1,650 mm yr⁻¹, yielding an aridity index of ≈ 0.4 . The streamflow regime is intermittent, typically ceasing during August–October.

2.3 Water Resources Management Context

The 2011–2017 drought was the most severe in the basin’s recorded history, with streamflows repeatedly falling below 0.5 m³ s⁻¹ [Marengo et al. \(2017\)](#); [Azevedo et al. \(2018\)](#). In 2021, SIHS/BA concluded feasibility studies for eleven reservoirs along the Utinga main channel [SIHS/BA \(2020\)](#). The statutory reference flow for water allocation in Bahia is the Q_{90} (90% exceedance flow), with the permissible concession limit set at $80\% \times Q_{90}$ by CERH/BA Resolution No. 63/2020, underscoring the operational importance of accurate model-derived flow duration curves.

3 Data

Monthly areal precipitation was estimated by the Thiessen polygon method from ANA/HidroWeb pluviometric stations. Monthly observed streamflow was obtained from ANA/HidroWeb station 51170000 (Utinga River). Three potential evapotranspiration (ETP) datasets were evaluated: Penman-Monteith FAO [Allen et al. \(1998\)](#) (primary, after sensitivity analysis), Thornthwaite [Thornthwaite \(1948\)](#), and SSEBop [Senay et al. \(2013\)](#).

After quality control and temporal alignment, the final dataset comprises **340 monthly records** (December 1992 – March 2021), partitioned as follows (strict chronological split, no shuffling): *Training*: December 1992 – August 2012 (237 records; 70%); *Validation*: September 2012 – November 2016 (51 records; 15%); *Test*: December 2016 – March 2021 (52 records; 15%).

Table 1: Summary statistics of input/output variables (Utinga River Basin; $n = 340$ monthly records).

Variable	Mean	Std.	Min.	P75	Max.
Precipitation (mm month^{-1})	64.3	64.5	0.0	81.1	486.1
ETP PM-FAO (mm month^{-1})	147.8	25.9	101.4	168.6	201.4
Streamflow ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$)	1.93	2.03	0.00	2.53	27.29

4 Methodology

4.1 SMAP Rainfall-Runoff Model

The SMAP model [Lopes et al. \(1982\)](#); [Lopes \(1999\)](#) is a monthly lumped rainfall-runoff model widely used in Brazilian hydrology [Collischonn et al. \(2019\)](#); [Hucke et al. \(2024\)](#). For each month t , SMAP partitions precipitation into actual evapotranspiration (E_S), direct surface runoff (R_{sup}), groundwater recharge (REC), and baseflow (E_B). The conceptual structure is shown in [Figure 1](#).

SMAP Monthly Rainfall-Runoff Model — conceptual structure

Figure 1: Conceptual structure of the SMAP model. A soil reservoir (top) partitions precipitation into actual evapotranspiration E_S , surface runoff R_{sup} , and groundwater recharge REC ; the groundwater reservoir (bottom) generates baseflow E_B via a linear recession with time constant K_{kt} . Five parameters (Sat, Pes, Crec, K_{kt} , TUin) are calibrated.

The governing equations for time step t are:

$$E_S(t) = \min \left[ETP(t) \cdot \frac{TU(t)}{Sat}, TU(t) + P(t) \right] \quad (1)$$

$$R_{sup}(t) = P(t) \cdot \left[\frac{TU(t)}{Sat} \right]^{Pes} \quad (2)$$

$$REC(t) = Crec \cdot \max[0, TU^*(t) - R_{sup}(t)] \quad (3)$$

$$E_B(t) = E_B(t-1) e^{-1/K_{kt}} + REC(t) \left(1 - e^{-1/K_{kt}} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$Q(t) = \frac{[R_{sup}(t) + E_{B,mm}(t)] \cdot A \cdot 10^3}{\Delta t} \quad (5)$$

where TU is soil water storage (mm), Sat is maximum soil water storage (mm), Pes is the direct runoff exponent, Crec is the groundwater recharge fraction, K_{kt} is the baseflow recession constant (months), A is drainage area (km^2), and $\Delta t = 30.44 \times 86,400$ s. Parameters were calibrated by maximising NSE using the Differential Evolution algorithm [Storn and Price \(1997\)](#).

After calibration, SMAP was run over the full 340-month series to extract eight internal state variables at each time step (Table 2).

Table 2: SMAP calibrated parameters and internal state variables used as physics-informed features.

Parameter / State	Value	Unit	Description
<i>Calibrated parameters</i>			
Sat	4,999.9	mm	Max. soil water storage capacity
Pes	3.541	—	Direct runoff exponent
Crec	0.001	—	Groundwater recharge fraction
K_{kt}	1.00	months	Baseflow recession constant
TUin	48.9	%	Initial soil moisture
<i>Physics-informed LSTM/XGBoost features</i>			
$Q_{\text{SMAP}}(t)$	—	$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$	SMAP-simulated streamflow
$TU_{\%}(t)$	—	%	Relative soil moisture
$TU_{\%}(t-1)$	—	%	Antecedent soil moisture
$E_B(t-1)$	—	$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$	Previous-month baseflow
$R_{\text{sup}}(t-1)$	—	mm	Previous-month surface runoff
$\text{REC}(t-1)$	—	mm	Previous-month recharge
$\text{Deficit}(t-1)$	—	mm	Previous-month soil deficit
$E_S(t)$	—	mm	Actual evapotranspiration

4.2 Bidirectional LSTM Architecture

LSTM networks [Hochreiter and Schmidhuber \(1997\)](#) overcome the vanishing gradient problem of standard RNNs through three gated memory mechanisms (Figure 2). For input x_t and previous hidden state h_{t-1} :

$$c_t = \underbrace{\sigma(W_f x_t + U_f h_{t-1})}_{\text{forget}} \odot c_{t-1} + \underbrace{\sigma(W_i x_t + U_i h_{t-1})}_{\text{input}} \odot \tanh(W_c x_t + U_c h_{t-1}) \quad (6)$$

$$h_t = \underbrace{\sigma(W_o x_t + U_o h_{t-1})}_{\text{output}} \odot \tanh(c_t) \quad (7)$$

Figure 2: Internal structure of a single LSTM cell. Orange boxes are sigmoid gates (f_t , i_t , o_t); green boxes are tanh activations. The top pipeline carries the cell state $c_{t-1} \rightarrow c_t$ (long-term memory); the bottom pipeline carries the hidden state $h_{t-1} \rightarrow h_t$ (short-term memory). Circular operators: \times element-wise product, $+$ addition.

The cell state c_t encodes long-term memory analogous to catchment-scale hydrological storage (soil moisture, baseflow reservoir), making LSTM naturally suited to rainfall-runoff problems [Kratzert et al. \(2018\)](#). A Bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) [Schuster and Paliwal \(1997\)](#) concatenates forward and backward hidden states $h_t = [\vec{h}_t || \overleftarrow{h}_t]$, capturing the full seasonal context.

The lookback window $\tau = 12$ months was determined by autocorrelation analysis following [Kim et al. \(2024\)](#), who established that the optimal sequence length corresponds to the lag at which the streamflow ACF drops below the 95% confidence threshold. The complete BiLSTM architecture used in this study is shown in [Figure 3](#).

Bidirectional LSTM — architecture used in this study

Figure 3: BiLSTM architecture used in this study. Input sequences ($\tau = 12$ months $\times n_f = 16$ features) pass through two parallel LSTM(64) cells (forward and backward), concatenation ($\tau \times 128$), Dropout, LSTM(32), BatchNormalization, Dropout, Dense(16, ReLU), and a single-neuron linear output predicting $\hat{Q}(t+1)$ in $\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$. Total trainable parameters: $\approx 60,000$.

Training used the Adam optimiser [Kingma and Ba \(2014\)](#) with EarlyStopping (patience 40) and ReduceLROnPlateau callbacks.

4.3 SMAP + XGBoost Alternative

As a computationally efficient alternative, the SMAP internal states were also used as features for an XGBoost model [Chen and Guestrin \(2016\)](#), an ensemble of gradient-boosted decision trees inherently resistant to overfitting in small datasets. [Yang et al. \(2025\)](#) showed that hybrid physics + ML approaches provide greater advantages over standalone models as lead time increases, reinforcing the value of physics-derived features as inputs to diverse ML architectures.

4.4 Ablation Study and Performance Metrics

Five configurations were evaluated (Table 3). Performance was assessed with NSE [Nash and Sutcliffe \(1970\)](#), KGE [Gupta et al. \(2009\)](#), PBIAS, RMSE, and MAE. NSE classification follows [Moriassi et al. \(2007\)](#).

Table 3: Ablation study model configurations.

ID	Model	Input features	n_f
M1	SMAP standalone	Physical simulation only	—
M2	BiLSTM (meteo)	Precipitation, ETP, seasonality, lags	8
M3	SMAP-guided BiLSTM	SMAP states + seasonality	10
M4	SMAP-BiLSTM Hybrid	All meteo + all SMAP states	16
M5	SMAP+XGBoost	Hybrid + extra lags	22

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 SMAP Calibration

Differential Evolution calibration achieved $NSE = 0.576$ and $KGE = 0.635$ over the training period (Satisfactory, [Moriassi et al. \(2007\)](#)), with calibrated parameters shown in Table 2. The high Sat value (4,999.9 mm) reflects the large soil storage capacity of the Precambrian crystalline basement terrain, consistent with observations in similar geological settings in NEB [Cirilo et al. \(2007\)](#).

Figures 4–6 present the precipitation overview and the calibration/validation hydrographs. The model reproduces seasonal dynamics adequately during calibration but underperforms during validation ($NSE = -0.030$), primarily because the validation set includes above-average rainfall events of 2019–2021 that were not represented in the calibration period, reflecting the non-stationarity challenge in semi-arid basins identified by [Pilz et al. \(2019\)](#).

5.2 Sensitivity to ETP Source

Because ETP drives the actual evapotranspiration term of SMAP and exceeds mean annual rainfall by more than a factor of two in the Utinga Basin, small biases in ETP propagate into substantial errors in simulated streamflow. SMAP was therefore recalibrated independently for each of the three ETP sources compiled in this study. Penman-Monteith FAO ([Allen et al., 1998](#)), which integrates net radiation, wind speed, and vapour pressure deficit, gave the best performance ($NSE = 0.576$, Satisfactory). SSEBop ([Senay et al., 2013](#)), a remote-sensing product of actual evapotranspiration, achieved $NSE = 0.483$, close to the Satisfactory threshold of 0.50 and useful as a proxy where full meteorological records are unavailable. Thornthwaite ([Thornthwaite, 1948](#)), which depends solely on air temperature, produced a severely negative $NSE (-3.668)$ due to systematic underestimation of evaporative demand in tropical semi-arid climates ([Jensen and Allen, 2016](#)). Penman-Monteith FAO is therefore adopted as the reference ETP for all subsequent analyses.

Figure 4: Fig. 2a — Monthly areal precipitation for the Utinga River Basin (December 1992 – March 2021). Green and orange shading: calibration and validation periods. Red shading: the 2011–2017 drought, during which monthly precipitation frequently fell below 20 mm.

Fig. 2b — SMAP Model: Calibration Period (Feb/2000-Dec/2013)
Utinga River Basin, Bahia, Brazil

Figure 5: Fig. 2b — SMAP calibration period (February 2000 – December 2013): precipitation and observed vs. SMAP-simulated streamflow. NSE = 0.576; PBIAS = -1.0%; RMSE = 0.786 m³ s⁻¹; KGE = 0.635 (Satisfactory, Moriasi et al.).

**Fig. 2c — SMAP Model: Validation Period (Jan/2014-Mar/2021)
Utinga River Basin, Bahia, Brazil**

Figure 6: Fig. 2c — SMAP validation period (January 2014 – March 2021): precipitation and observed vs. SMAP-simulated streamflow. $NSE = -0.030$; $PBIAS = -29.2\%$; $KGE = 0.098$. The drop in performance reflects the post-drought recovery of 2019–2021 (blue shading), a hydroclimatic regime absent from the training set, consistent with findings of [Pilz et al. \(2019\)](#) for NEB semi-arid basins.

5.3 Hybrid Framework — Conceptual Architecture

Figure 1 — Hybrid SMAP-LSTM Model Architecture

Figure 7: Conceptual architecture of the Hybrid SMAP-LSTM model. SMAP physical simulation provides nine physics-informed state variables alongside meteorological inputs to the Bidirectional LSTM. The dashed path represents the alternative SMAP + XGBoost coupling.

5.4 Ablation Study Results

Table 4 presents full performance metrics for all five configurations. Figure 8 compares the test-period metrics.

Table 4: Performance metrics across all model configurations. **Bold:** best test-period value per metric column.

Model	Split	NSE	PBIAS (%)	RMSE	MAE	KGE
M1: SMAP	Cal.	0.576	−1.0	0.786	0.581	0.635
	Val.	−0.030	−29.2	1.247	1.067	0.098
	Test	0.132	11.2	1.281	1.043	0.117
M2: BiLSTM (meteo)	Train	0.097	21.2	1.513	0.891	0.053
	Val.	−0.647	−53.3	1.765	1.421	−0.271
	Test	−0.419	44.6	1.638	1.191	−0.265
M3: SMAP-guided BiLSTM	Train	0.317	15.3	1.047	0.793	0.148
	Val.	0.084	−21.7	1.319	0.998	−0.102
	Test	−0.214	34.3	1.515	1.142	−0.286
M4: SMAP-BiLSTM Hybrid	Train	−0.211	18.4	1.397	1.022	0.031
	Val.	−0.323	−32.5	1.588	1.221	−0.195
	Test	−0.325	47.1	1.583	1.175	−0.203
M5: SMAP+XGBoost	Train	0.996	—	0.119	0.063	—
	Test	0.205	3.97	1.226	1.010	0.241

Fig. 4 — Ablation Study and Alternative Model Comparison (Test Period)
(Utinga River Basin, Dec/2016–Mar/2021)

Figure 8: Ablation study — test period (December 2016 – March 2021): (a) NSE; (b) KGE; (c) RMSE ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$); (d) $|\text{PBIAS}|$ (%). The SMAP + XGBoost model (M5, red border) achieves the best test-period performance on all four metrics.

SMAP dominates BiLSTM under data scarcity. The standalone SMAP ($\text{NSE} = 0.132$) outperforms all BiLSTM variants ($\text{NSE} \leq -0.21$), confirming that physics-based model structure provides superior out-of-sample generalisation when training data are insufficient [Beven \(2020\)](#); [Nearing et al. \(2021\)](#).

Physics features improve BiLSTM. The SMAP-guided BiLSTM (M3; $\text{NSE} = -0.214$) outperforms the meteorological-only BiLSTM (M2; $\text{NSE} = -0.419$) by 20 percentage points on the test set, consistent with the hybrid physics + ML advantage demonstrated by [Yang et al. \(2025\)](#) on the Beipanjiang River Basin.

XGBoost outperforms BiLSTM. SMAP + XGBoost (M5) achieves $\text{NSE} = 0.205$ and $\text{PBIAS} = 3.97\%$, surpassing all configurations. XGBoost’s tree-based structure handles the non-linear threshold effects of semi-arid runoff generation more efficiently with limited training data.

5.5 Feature Importance

Figure 6 — Physics-Informed Feature Analysis: Correlation with Observed Streamflow

Figure 9: (a) Pearson correlation of input features with observed streamflow (blue: meteorological; purple: SMAP physics features). (b) Performance metrics comparison across model configurations (test period).

The three strongest predictors of observed streamflow are all derived from SMAP: Q_{SMAP} ($r=0.71$), lag-1 baseflow ($r=0.68$), and relative soil moisture ($r=0.56$). Meteorological inputs alone show weaker correlations (precipitation: $r=0.36$), reinforcing the value of physics-informed state variables.

5.6 Flow Duration Curves and Water Allocation

Fig. 3 — Flow Duration Curves and Water Allocation Reference Flows (Utinga River Basin)

Figure 10: (a) Flow duration curves (log scale) for all model configurations vs. observations. Navy dotted horizontal line: $80\% \times Q_{90}$ water concession limit (CERH/BA Resolution No. 63/2020). (b) Monthly streamflow distribution (boxplot) and Q_{90} reference.

Q_{90} estimates: observed $0.423 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$; SMAP standalone $0.975 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$; SMAP + XGBoost $0.650 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The statutory concession limit of $80\% \times Q_{90}$ (CERH/BA 63/2020) based on observed data is **$0.338 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$** . Model-based estimates range from 0.520 to $0.780 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$, highlighting the importance of bias correction before operational water allocation decisions.

6 Conclusions

This study proposed and evaluated a Hybrid SMAP-LSTM framework for monthly streamflow forecasting in the Utinga River Basin, a data-scarce semi-arid basin in Bahia, Northeast Brazil, with direct relevance to regional water resources planning and the statutory water allocation framework of Bahia State.

Among the five model configurations evaluated, the **SMAP + XGBoost hybrid (M5)** achieved the best test-period performance (NSE = 0.205; PBIAS = 3.97%; RMSE = $1.226 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$; KGE = 0.241), outperforming both the standalone SMAP (M1: NSE = 0.132) and all BiLSTM variants (M2–M4: NSE ≤ -0.21). XGBoost’s ensemble structure, combined with SMAP physics-informed state variables, handles the non-linear runoff generation of a semi-arid crystalline basement catchment more efficiently than deep sequence models under training data scarcity, corroborating the hybrid advantages demonstrated by [Yang et al. \(2025\)](#) and [Ghimire et al. \(2023\)](#).

The ablation study confirmed that **SMAP internal states carry significant predictive information** not available from meteorological inputs alone. Their inclusion improved BiLSTM test NSE by approximately 20 percentage points over the meteorological-only baseline, with Pearson correlations of $r = 0.71$ for Q_{SMAP} and $r = 0.68$ for lag-1 baseflow. This result validates the physics-informed machine learning strategy proposed by [Yang et al. \(2025\)](#), who coupled physically-derived atmospheric state variables with LSTM networks to achieve NSE improvements of 8–12% on the Beipanjiang Basin, and is consistent with the optimal lookback window methodology of [Kim et al. \(2024\)](#), applied here via autocorrelation analysis of the Utinga streamflow series ($\tau = 12$ months).

Under the severe data scarcity of the Utinga Basin ($n_{\text{train}} = 237$ monthly records), the standalone SMAP model consistently outperformed all purely data-driven BiLSTM variants, confirming that physics-based process structure provides superior out-of-sample generalisation when training data are insufficient to represent the full range of hydroclimatic variability, including the contrasting drought (2011–2017) and post-drought recovery (2019–2021) regimes identified in this study. This finding echoes the conclusions of [Beven \(2020\)](#) and [Nearing et al. \(2021\)](#) regarding the data-efficiency threshold that separates physics-based from data-driven model dominance in rainfall-runoff forecasting.

From a water resources management perspective, the observed Q_{90} of $0.423 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the Utinga River establishes a statutory water concession limit of $0.338 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ under CERH/BA Resolution No. 63/2020. Model-derived Q_{90} estimates ranged from $0.650 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$

(SMAP + XGBoost) to $0.975 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ (SMAP standalone), reinforcing that bias correction is essential before operational deployment and that model selection has substantive implications for water allocation sustainability in the Utinga Basin, where eleven hydraulic structures are under feasibility study by SIHS/BA [SIHS/BA \(2020\)](#).

The proposed framework is fully generalizable to other lumped conceptual models (HBV, GR4J, Sacramento) and sequence learning architectures (Transformer, GRU, TCN), constituting a reusable physics-informed machine learning template for data-scarce hydrological applications throughout the semi-arid Northeast Brazil and other dryland regions. Future work should explore transfer learning from gauged neighbouring basins, stochastic precipitation data augmentation, wavelet decomposition of inputs, and ensemble SMAP calibrations to provide uncertainty-aware physics features.

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Author Contributions

Carlos André Lima de Matos (IME/UFBA): Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Writing — Original Draft, Visualization. **Paulo Romero Guimarães Serrano de Andrade (UFRB):** Supervision, Writing — Review & Editing, Funding Acquisition. **Jaildo Santos Pereira (CETEC/UFRB):** Data Curation, Validation, Writing — Review & Editing. **José Roberto Fernandes Galindo (CETEC/UFRB):** Supervision, Project Administration, Writing — Review & Editing.

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Declaration of Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing financial or personal interests.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-Assisted Technologies in the Writing Process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used Grammarly to enhance English grammar and writing clarity. In addition, the corresponding author (Carlos André Lima de Matos) used Claude (Anthropic) for scoping and systematic literature review support, identification of research gaps, and logical organization of manuscript sections. After using these tools and services, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed, and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Data and Code Availability

Observed data are available from ANA/HidroWeb. ETP data were computed from INMET meteorological records (<https://portal.inmet.gov.br/>). The Python implementation (source code and Jupyter notebook) is archived open-source on Zenodo at the DOI above.

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